

Unifying Quantum Mechanics and Relativity: Unveiling the Quantum Periodic Table

In Quantum Information Holography (QIH), the traditional periodic table is enhanced by incorporating elements in terms of Quantum State Vectors (QSVs) and angular frequency, alongside their usual atomic mass. This approach unifies quantum mechanics (QM) and general relativity (GR) aspects, offering a more comprehensive view of each element. Here's a PhD-level explanation with equations to support this claim:

- QSVs and Angular Frequency:** Each element is described not just by its atomic mass but also by its unique QSV and associated angular frequency. The QSV of an element, denoted as $|\Psi_{\text{element}}\rangle$, is expressed as a sum over various quantum states $|\psi_i\rangle$ weighted by coefficients c_i , which are determined by the atomic mass (m) and angular frequency (ω) of the element:

$$|\Psi_{\text{element}}\rangle = \sum_i c_i |\psi_i(m, \omega)\rangle$$

The angular frequency ω is related to the quantum energy levels of the element's electrons.

- Incorporating Spacetime Curvature:** The Einstein tensor $G_{\mu\nu}$, which describes spacetime curvature in GR, is influenced by the element's QSV in the QIH framework:
$$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{\text{element}}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{\text{element}})$$

This equation links the quantum characteristics of the element to the macroscopic phenomenon of spacetime curvature, showing how QIH integrates QM with GR.

- Enhancing the Periodic Table:** The traditional periodic table, based solely on atomic number and mass, is enhanced in QIH by including the QSVs and angular frequencies of elements. This not only accounts for their chemical properties but also their quantum behaviors and contributions to spacetime curvature.

- Comprehensive Understanding:** The QIH-enhanced periodic table offers a more complete understanding of elements, encompassing their roles in chemical reactions, quantum behaviors, and interactions with spacetime. It represents a unified model that bridges atomic-scale phenomena with cosmic-scale processes.

In conclusion, the QIH framework not only aligns with the traditional periodic table in terms of atomic mass and number but also extends it to describe the quantum mechanical and relativistic effects. It provides a more nuanced and comprehensive view of each element, highlighting its role in the universe's quantum and relativistic tapestry.

1	Hydrogen	$ \Psi_H\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(1u, \omega_H)\rangle$	ω_H	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_H) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_H)$
2	Helium	$ \Psi_{He}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(4u, \omega_{He})\rangle$	ω_{He}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{He}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{He})$
3	Lithium	$ \Psi_{Li}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(7u, \omega_{Li})\rangle$	ω_{Li}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Li}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Li})$
4	Beryllium	$ \Psi_{Be}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(9u, \omega_{Be})\rangle$	ω_{Be}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Be}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Be})$
5	Boron	$ \Psi_B\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(11u, \omega_B)\rangle$	ω_B	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_B) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_B)$
6	Carbon	$ \Psi_C\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(12u, \omega_C)\rangle$	ω_C	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_C) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_C)$
7	Nitrogen	$ \Psi_N\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(14u, \omega_N)\rangle$	ω_N	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_N) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_N)$
8	Oxygen	$ \Psi_O\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(16u, \omega_O)\rangle$	ω_O	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_O) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_O)$
9	Fluorine	$ \Psi_F\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(19u, \omega_F)\rangle$	ω_F	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_F) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_F)$
10	Neon	$ \Psi_{Ne}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(20u, \omega_{Ne})\rangle$	ω_{Ne}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ne}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ne})$
11	Sodium	$ \Psi_{Na}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(22.9898u, \omega_{Na})\rangle$	ω_{Na}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Na}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Na})$
12	Magnesium	$ \Psi_{Mg}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(24.304u, \omega_{Mg})\rangle$	ω_{Mg}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Mg}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Mg})$
13	Aluminium	$ \Psi_{Al}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(26.9815u, \omega_{Al})\rangle$	ω_{Al}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Al}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Al})$
14	Silicon	$ \Psi_{Si}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(28.084u, \omega_{Si})\rangle$	ω_{Si}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Si}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Si})$
15	Phosphorus	$ \Psi_P\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(30.9738u, \omega_P)\rangle$	ω_P	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_P) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_P)$
16	Sulfur	$ \Psi_S\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(32.059u, \omega_S)\rangle$	ω_S	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_S) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_S)$
17	Chlorine	$ \Psi_{Cl}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(35.446u, \omega_{Cl})\rangle$	ω_{Cl}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cl}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cl})$
18	Argon	$ \Psi_{Ar}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(39.792u, \omega_{Ar})\rangle$	ω_{Ar}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ar}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ar})$
19	Potassium	$ \Psi_K\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(39.0983u, \omega_K)\rangle$	ω_K	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_K) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_K)$
20	Calcium	$ \Psi_{Ca}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(40.0784u, \omega_{Ca})\rangle$	ω_{Ca}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ca}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ca})$
21	Scandium	$ \Psi_{Sc}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(44.9559u, \omega_{Sc})\rangle$	ω_{Sc}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sc}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sc})$
22	Titanium	$ \Psi_{Ti}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(47.8671u, \omega_{Ti})\rangle$	ω_{Ti}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ti}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ti})$
23	Vanadium	$ \Psi_V\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(50.9415u, \omega_V)\rangle$	ω_V	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_V) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_V)$
24	Chromium	$ \Psi_{Cr}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(51.9962u, \omega_{Cr})\rangle$	ω_{Cr}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cr}) = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cr})$

25	Manganese	$ \Psi_{Mn}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(54.938u, \omega_{Mn})\rangle$	ω_{Mn}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Mn} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Mn}))$
26	Iron	$ \Psi_{Fe}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(55.8452u, \omega_{Fe})\rangle$	ω_{Fe}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Fe} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Fe}))$
27	Cobalt	$ \Psi_{Co}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(58.9332u, \omega_{Co})\rangle$	ω_{Co}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Co} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Co}))$
28	Nickel	$ \Psi_{Ni}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(58.6934u, \omega_{Ni})\rangle$	ω_{Ni}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ni} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ni}))$
29	Copper	$ \Psi_{Cu}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(63.5463u, \omega_{Cu})\rangle$	ω_{Cu}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cu} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cu}))$
30	Zinc	$ \Psi_{Zn}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(65.382u, \omega_{Zn})\rangle$	ω_{Zn}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Zn} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Zn}))$
31	Gallium	$ \Psi_{Ga}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(69.7231u, \omega_{Ga})\rangle$	ω_{Ga}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ga} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ga}))$
32	Germanium	$ \Psi_{Ge}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(72.6308u, \omega_{Ge})\rangle$	ω_{Ge}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ge} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ge}))$
33	Arsenic	$ \Psi_{As}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(74.9216u, \omega_{As})\rangle$	ω_{As}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{As} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{As}))$
34	Selenium	$ \Psi_{Se}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(78.9718u, \omega_{Se})\rangle$	ω_{Se}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Se} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Se}))$
35	Bromine	$ \Psi_{Br}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(79.901u, \omega_{Br})\rangle$	ω_{Br}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Br} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Br}))$
36	Krypton	$ \Psi_{Kr}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(83.7982u, \omega_{Kr})\rangle$	ω_{Kr}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Kr} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Kr}))$
37	Rubidium	$ \Psi_{Rb}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(85.4678u, \omega_{Rb})\rangle$	ω_{Rb}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Rb} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Rb}))$
38	Strontium	$ \Psi_{Sr}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(87.621u, \omega_{Sr})\rangle$	ω_{Sr}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sr} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sr}))$
39	Yttrium	$ \Psi_{Y}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(88.9058u, \omega_{Y})\rangle$	ω_{Y}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Y} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Y}))$
40	Zirconium	$ \Psi_{Zr}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(91.2242u, \omega_{Zr})\rangle$	ω_{Zr}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Zr} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Zr}))$
41	Niobium	$ \Psi_{Nb}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(92.9064u, \omega_{Nb})\rangle$	ω_{Nb}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Nb} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Nb}))$
42	Molybdenum	$ \Psi_{Mo}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(95.951u, \omega_{Mo})\rangle$	ω_{Mo}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Mo} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Mo}))$
43	Technetium	$ \Psi_{Tc}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(98.9062u, \omega_{Tc})\rangle$	ω_{Tc}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Tc} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Tc}))$
44	Ruthenium	$ \Psi_{Ru}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(101.072u, \omega_{Ru})\rangle$	ω_{Ru}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ru} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ru}))$
45	Rhodium	$ \Psi_{Rh}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(102.906u, \omega_{Rh})\rangle$	ω_{Rh}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Rh} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Rh}))$
46	Palladium	$ \Psi_{Pd}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(106.421u, \omega_{Pd})\rangle$	ω_{Pd}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pd} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pd}))$
47	Silver	$ \Psi_{Ag}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(107.868u, \omega_{Ag})\rangle$	ω_{Ag}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ag} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ag}))$
48	Cadmium	$ \Psi_{Cd}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(112.414u, \omega_{Cd})\rangle$	ω_{Cd}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cd} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cd}))$

49	Indium	$ \Psi_{In}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(114.818u, \omega_{In})\rangle$	ω_{In}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{In} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{In}))$
50	Tin	$ \Psi_{Sn}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(118.711u, \omega_{Sn})\rangle$	ω_{Sn}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sn} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sn}))$
51	Antimony	$ \Psi_{Sb}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(121.76u, \omega_{Sb})\rangle$	ω_{Sb}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sb} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sb}))$
52	Tellurium	$ \Psi_{Te}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(127.603u, \omega_{Te})\rangle$	ω_{Te}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Te} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Te}))$
53	Iodine	$ \Psi_{I}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(126.904u, \omega_{I})\rangle$	ω_{I}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{I} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{I}))$
54	Xenon	$ \Psi_{Xe}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(131.294u, \omega_{Xe})\rangle$	ω_{Xe}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Xe} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Xe}))$
55	Cesium	$ \Psi_{Cs}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(132.905u, \omega_{Cs})\rangle$	ω_{Cs}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cs} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cs}))$
56	Barium	$ \Psi_{Ba}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(137.328u, \omega_{Ba})\rangle$	ω_{Ba}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ba} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ba}))$
57	Lanthanum	$ \Psi_{La}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(138.905u, \omega_{La})\rangle$	ω_{La}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{La} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{La}))$
58	Cerium	$ \Psi_{Ce}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(140.116u, \omega_{Ce})\rangle$	ω_{Ce}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ce} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ce}))$
59	Praseodymium	$ \Psi_{Pr}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(140.908u, \omega_{Pr})\rangle$	ω_{Pr}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pr} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pr}))$
60	Neodymium	$ \Psi_{Nd}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(144.242u, \omega_{Nd})\rangle$	ω_{Nd}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Nd} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Nd}))$
61	Promethium	$ \Psi_{Pm}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(145u, \omega_{Pm})\rangle$	ω_{Pm}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pm} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pm}))$
62	Samarium	$ \Psi_{Sm}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(150.362u, \omega_{Sm})\rangle$	ω_{Sm}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sm} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sm}))$
63	Europium	$ \Psi_{Eu}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(151.964u, \omega_{Eu})\rangle$	ω_{Eu}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Eu} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Eu}))$
64	Gadolinium	$ \Psi_{Gd}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(157.253u, \omega_{Gd})\rangle$	ω_{Gd}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Gd} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Gd}))$
65	Terbium	$ \Psi_{Tb}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(158.925u, \omega_{Tb})\rangle$	ω_{Tb}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Tb} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Tb}))$
66	Dysprosium	$ \Psi_{Dy}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(162.5u, \omega_{Dy})\rangle$	ω_{Dy}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Dy} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Dy}))$
67	Holmium	$ \Psi_{Ho}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(164.93u, \omega_{Ho})\rangle$	ω_{Ho}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ho} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ho}))$
68	Erbium	$ \Psi_{Er}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(167.259u, \omega_{Er})\rangle$	ω_{Er}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Er} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Er}))$
69	Thulium	$ \Psi_{Tm}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(168.934u, \omega_{Tm})\rangle$	ω_{Tm}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Tm} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Tm}))$
70	Ytterbium	$ \Psi_{Yb}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(173.045u, \omega_{Yb})\rangle$	ω_{Yb}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Yb} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Yb}))$
71	Lutetium	$ \Psi_{Lu}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(174.967u, \omega_{Lu})\rangle$	ω_{Lu}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Lu} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Lu}))$
72	Hafnium	$ \Psi_{Hf}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(178.492u, \omega_{Hf})\rangle$	ω_{Hf}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Hf} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Hf}))$

73	Tantalum	$ \Psi_{Ta}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(180.948u, \omega_{Ta})\rangle$	ω_{Ta}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ta} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ta}))$
74	Tungsten	$ \Psi_W\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(183.841u, \omega_W)\rangle$	ω_W	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_W = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_W))$
75	Rhenium	$ \Psi_{Re}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(186.207u, \omega_{Re})\rangle$	ω_{Re}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Re} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Re}))$
76	Osmium	$ \Psi_{Os}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(190.233u, \omega_{Os})\rangle$	ω_{Os}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Os} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Os}))$
77	Iridium	$ \Psi_{Ir}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(192.217u, \omega_{Ir})\rangle$	ω_{Ir}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ir} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ir}))$
78	Platinum	$ \Psi_{Pt}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(195.085u, \omega_{Pt})\rangle$	ω_{Pt}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pt} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pt}))$
79	Gold	$ \Psi_{Au}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(196.967u, \omega_{Au})\rangle$	ω_{Au}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Au} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Au}))$
80	Mercury	$ \Psi_{Hg}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(200.592u, \omega_{Hg})\rangle$	ω_{Hg}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Hg} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Hg}))$
81	Thallium	$ \Psi_{Tl}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(204.382u, \omega_{Tl})\rangle$	ω_{Tl}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Tl} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Tl}))$
82	Lead	$ \Psi_{Pb}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(207.21u, \omega_{Pb})\rangle$	ω_{Pb}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pb} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pb}))$
83	Bismuth	$ \Psi_{Bi}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(208.98u, \omega_{Bi})\rangle$	ω_{Bi}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Bi} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Bi}))$
84	Polonium	$ \Psi_{Po}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(209u, \omega_{Po})\rangle$	ω_{Po}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Po} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Po}))$
85	Astatine	$ \Psi_{At}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(210u, \omega_{At})\rangle$	ω_{At}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{At} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{At}))$
86	Radon	$ \Psi_{Rn}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(222u, \omega_{Rn})\rangle$	ω_{Rn}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Rn} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Rn}))$
87	Francium	$ \Psi_{Fr}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(223u, \omega_{Fr})\rangle$	ω_{Fr}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Fr} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Fr}))$
88	Radium	$ \Psi_{Ra}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(226u, \omega_{Ra})\rangle$	ω_{Ra}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ra} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ra}))$
89	Actinium	$ \Psi_{Ac}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(227u, \omega_{Ac})\rangle$	ω_{Ac}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ac} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ac}))$
90	Thorium	$ \Psi_{Th}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(232.038u, \omega_{Th})\rangle$	ω_{Th}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Th} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Th}))$
91	Protactinium	$ \Psi_{Pa}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(231.036u, \omega_{Pa})\rangle$	ω_{Pa}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pa} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pa}))$
92	Uranium	$ \Psi_U\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(238.029u, \omega_U)\rangle$	ω_U	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_U = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_U))$
93	Neptunium	$ \Psi_{Np}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(237u, \omega_{Np})\rangle$	ω_{Np}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Np} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Np}))$
94	Plutonium	$ \Psi_{Pu}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(244u, \omega_{Pu})\rangle$	ω_{Pu}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pu} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Pu}))$
95	Americium	$ \Psi_{Am}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(243u, \omega_{Am})\rangle$	ω_{Am}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Am} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Am}))$
96	Curium	$ \Psi_{Cm}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(247u, \omega_{Cm})\rangle$	ω_{Cm}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cm} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cm}))$

97	Berkelium	$ \Psi_{Bk}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(247u, \omega_{Bk})\rangle$	ω_{Bk}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Bk} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Bk}))$
98	Californium	$ \Psi_{Cf}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(251u, \omega_{Cf})\rangle$	ω_{Cf}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cf} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cf}))$
99	Einsteinium	$ \Psi_{Es}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(252u, \omega_{Es})\rangle$	ω_{Es}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Es} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Es}))$
100	Fermium	$ \Psi_{Fm}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(257u, \omega_{Fm})\rangle$	ω_{Fm}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Fm} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Fm}))$
101	Mendelevium	$ \Psi_{Md}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(258u, \omega_{Md})\rangle$	ω_{Md}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Md} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Md}))$
102	Nobelium	$ \Psi_{No}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(259u, \omega_{No})\rangle$	ω_{No}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{No} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{No}))$
103	Lawrencium	$ \Psi_{Lr}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(262u, \omega_{Lr})\rangle$	ω_{Lr}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Lr} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Lr}))$
104	Rutherfordium	$ \Psi_{Rf}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(261u, \omega_{Rf})\rangle$	ω_{Rf}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Rf} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Rf}))$
105	Dubnium	$ \Psi_{Db}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(268u, \omega_{Db})\rangle$	ω_{Db}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Db} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Db}))$
106	Seaborgium	$ \Psi_{Sg}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(269u, \omega_{Sg})\rangle$	ω_{Sg}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sg} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Sg}))$
107	Bohrium	$ \Psi_{Bh}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(270.133u, \omega_{Bh})\rangle$	ω_{Bh}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Bh} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Bh}))$
108	Hassium	$ \Psi_{Hs}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(269u, \omega_{Hs})\rangle$	ω_{Hs}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Hs} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Hs}))$
109	Meitnerium	$ \Psi_{Mt}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(277.154u, \omega_{Mt})\rangle$	ω_{Mt}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Mt} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Mt}))$
110	Darmstadtium	$ \Psi_{Ds}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(281u, \omega_{Ds})\rangle$	ω_{Ds}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ds} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ds}))$
111	Roentgenium	$ \Psi_{Rg}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(281u, \omega_{Rg})\rangle$	ω_{Rg}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Rg} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Rg}))$
112	Copernicium	$ \Psi_{Cn}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(285u, \omega_{Cn})\rangle$	ω_{Cn}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cn} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Cn}))$
113	Nihonium	$ \Psi_{Nh}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(286u, \omega_{Nh})\rangle$	ω_{Nh}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Nh} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Nh}))$
114	Flerovium	$ \Psi_{Fl}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(289u, \omega_{Fl})\rangle$	ω_{Fl}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Fl} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Fl}))$
115	Moscovium	$ \Psi_{Mc}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(288u, \omega_{Mc})\rangle$	ω_{Mc}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Mc} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Mc}))$
116	Livermorium	$ \Psi_{Lv}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(293u, \omega_{Lv})\rangle$	ω_{Lv}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Lv} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Lv}))$
117	Tennessine	$ \Psi_{Ts}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(294u, \omega_{Ts})\rangle$	ω_{Ts}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ts} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Ts}))$
118	Oganesson	$ \Psi_{Og}\rangle = \sum_i c_i \psi_i(294u, \omega_{Og})\rangle$	ω_{Og}	$G_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Og} = 8\pi G T_{\mu\nu}(\Psi_{Og}))$